

Complexation of Nickel-, Cobalt- and Copper(II) with L-Pyrrolidine-2-carboxylic Acid

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Pseudo-first order reactions are common in kinetics of analytical interest¹. Stopped-flow technique has been used for investigating the complexation reaction of L-pyrrolidine-2-carboxylic acid (excess excretion of which causes² mental retardation, renal disease, deafness etc.) with Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II}. A comprehensive kinetic study can provide useful information about the behaviour of these biochemical processes. The present investigation provides significant information regarding the various binding steps. K_{os} (outer sphere complex formation constant) and activation parameters corresponding to the interaction of various forms of L-pyrrolidine-2-carboxylic acid.

Results and Discussion

A general mechanism for the complexation involves an outer sphere complex formation between the metal ion and ligand followed by loss of a water molecule from the inner coordination sphere of the metal ion³ and an attack by the ligand,

leading to the rate law,

$$\frac{d}{dt} [ML^{2+}] = k_o K_{os} [M(H_2O)_6^{2+}] [L] \quad (3)$$

The two forms of the ligand, (HN⁺-O⁻) monoprotonated and (N-O⁻) deprotonated obtained as a result of dissociation of L-pyrrolidine-2-carboxylic acid react with Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II} in a stepwise manner (Scheme 1), where M is the metal ion.

Applying steady state approximation⁴ for intermediate species, rate can be expressed as

Rate =

$$k_{obs} \left\{ \frac{([H^+]^2 + K_1 [H^+] + K_1 K_2)}{K_1 [H^+]} \right\} = k_{12} k_{43} K_2 / [H^+] \quad (4)$$

Plots of left-hand-side value vs $[H^+]^{-1}$ were found linear at temperatures 25, 30, 35 and 40°. The values of k_{12} and k_{43} obtained from these plots along with the values of activation parameters, calculated from linear plots of $\log k/T$ vs $1/T$ are presented in Table 1.

Scheme 1

In Scheme 1, water exchange takes place only through the steps k_{12} and k_{43} . Therefore, water exchange rate can be written as

$$\text{Rate} = k_{12}[\text{HN}^+ - \text{O}^-] [\text{M(II)}] + k_{43}[\text{N} - \text{O}^-] [\text{M(II)}] \quad (5)$$

Because $k_{12} \ll k_{43}$, equation (5) reduces to

$$\text{Rate} = k_{43}[\text{N} - \text{O}^-] [\text{M(II)}] \quad (6)$$

Comparing equations (3) and (6) we get

$$k_{43} = K_{os} k_o \quad (7)$$

The value of K_{os} is calculated using Fuoss⁵ equation. The value of k_o at 25° were calculated to be 2.62×10^4 , 1.06×10^6 and $1.08 \times 10^9 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes respectively. Swift and Connick⁶ reported the corresponding values of k_o as 2.7×10^4 , 7.62×10^4 and $2.0 \times 10^8 \text{ s}^{-1}$ in the absence of any ligand.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF SPECIFIC RATE CONSTANTS AND THEIR ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE INTERACTION OF Ni^{II}, Co^{II} AND Cu^{II} WITH L-PYRROLIDINE-2-CARBOXYLIC ACID (LIGAND)

Temp °C	Ni ^{II} -ligand		Co ^{II} -ligand		Cu ^{II} -ligand	
	k_{12} M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	$k_{43} \times 10^{-4}$ M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	$k_{12} \times 10^{-1}$ M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	$k_{43} \times 10^{-6}$ M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	$k_{12} \times 10^{-1}$ M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	$k_{43} \times 10^{-9}$ M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
25	3.6	5.19	8.0	2.11	—	2.14
30	5.8	6.96	15.0	3.05	0.35	2.60
35	7.5	8.98	26.0	4.23	0.70	3.37
40	9.5	11.90	37.0	5.32	1.25	3.91
$\Delta H^\ddagger$ kJ mol ⁻¹	55.2	40.70	82.0	37.20	95.70	28.07
$\Delta S^\ddagger$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	-32.4	-49.00	36.0	-29.80	50.40	-0.70

NOTE

The values of specific rate constants k_{12} and k_{43} show that the reactivity of the deprotonated form of the ligand is very much greater than that for the zwitterionic form ($k_{43} > k_{12}$). This fact is further supported by the corresponding values of activation parameters. The negative values of $\Delta S^\ddagger$ can be attributed to the fact that the transition state for this complex is highly charged and which clearly shows that the reaction is between two oppositely charged ions.

Experimental

L-Pyrrolidine-2-carboxylic acid (Hi-media), KNO_3 and bromothymol blue (B.D.H.), $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (all Merck, G.R.) were used as such. pH of the solution was adjusted using 2,6-lutidine (Merck schuchardt) and HCl (Glaxo, A.R.). Triple-distilled water was used for preparing the solutions. Ionic strength of all reaction mixtures were kept constant at 0.1 M (KNO_3).

Stopped-flow kinetic experiments : Kinetic measurements were made on an Aminco Morrow stopped-flow spectrophotometer. The two driving syringes and reaction chamber of the stopped flow assembly were thermostated at 25, 30, 35 and $40 \pm 0.05^\circ$. Solutions of the metal ions and ligand were pushed into the observation cell and the changes brought about by reacting the solutions were monitored directly through a photo-multiplier tube and recorded on storage oscilloscope. Absorbance changes brought about by reaction of Ni^{II} and Co^{II} with the ligand were monitored at 620 nm. Since the absorbance changes were not large enough to be monitored directly, bromothymol blue was used as a pH indicator. Absorbance changes in the case of Cu^{II} -ligand reaction was monitored

at 390 nm and here no pH indicator was used since the absorbance change was large enough to be monitored directly. The reactions were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions, i.e. $[\text{M}(\text{II})] > [\text{L-pyrrolidine-2-carboxylic acid}]$ to ensure the formation of mono-complex only. The values of pseudo-first order rate constant (k'_{obs}) were evaluated from linear plots of $\log V$ vs time. Second order rate constants (k_{obs}) were evaluated from the relation,

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k'_{\text{obs}}/[\text{M}(\text{II})]$$

Blank experiments showed no absorbance change at requisite wavelength.

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